

1 **Reliability of stainless steel frames designed using the Direct Design Method**
2 **in serviceability limit states**

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8 **ABSTRACT**

9 Steel structures can be consistently and efficiently designed using system-based *design-by-analysis*
10 approaches such as the Direct Design Method. However, since direct design approaches lead to potentially
11 lighter structural configurations, they can also result in larger deformations under service loads. Thus,
12 greater attention may be required to serviceability limit states in structures designed using *design-by-*
13 *analysis* approaches than for structures designed elastically at their ultimate limit state following current
14 *two-stage* approaches, especially for materials showing highly nonlinear stress vs strain responses such
15 as stainless steel alloys. With the aim of assessing the influence of allowing larger deformations in the
16 ultimate limit state design of stainless steel structures, this paper presents an explicit analysis framework
17 for assessing serviceability reliability at system level. Using this framework, the paper investigates the
18 serviceability reliability of cold-formed stainless steel portal frames designed using the Direct Design
19 Method for different load cases, including the gravity load and the combined gravity plus wind load
20 combinations. The study considers six baseline frames covering the most common stainless steel
21 families and international design frameworks (i.e., Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks), for
22 which the reliability of vertical deflection and lateral drift serviceability limit states is investigated using
23 advanced numerical simulations and First-Order Reliability Methods. From the comparison of the
24 calculated average annual reliability indices and the relevant target reliabilities for the different design
25 frameworks, it was found that the reliability of stainless steel frames appears to be adequate for the
26 serviceability limit states investigated for the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks.

27 **KEYWORDS**

28 advanced analysis; deflections; reliability analysis; serviceability limit states; stainless steel structures;
29 structural reliability

30 HIGHLIGHTS

- 31 • A general framework for assessing the serviceability limit state reliability at system level is
32 presented.
- 33 • Vertical deflections under gravity loads and lateral drifts under wind loads are studied.
- 34 • Six baseline cold-formed frames, including the three main stainless steel families, are investigated.
- 35 • Reliability results are presented for the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks.
- 36 • Derived reliability indices are compared with suitable target values for each design framework.

37 1. INTRODUCTION

38 Serviceability limit states are conditions in which the normal use of structures is compromised due to
39 excessive deformations of components, local damage, damage to services or machinery and occupant
40 discomfort. The serviceability limit state criteria include deflections and vibrations, and although they
41 do not generally result in safety issues, they can have notable economic consequences and should be
42 carefully addressed in structural engineering practice. The main types of serviceability non-compliances
43 are related to the excessive deflection of horizontal members or lateral displacement of structures, in
44 which cases the limit state function can be written as per in Eq. 1, where δ_a is the allowable deflection
45 limit and $\Delta(t)$ is the deflection of the structure at time t due to the applied loading [1].

$$46 \qquad g = \delta_a - \Delta(t) \qquad \text{Eq. 1}$$

47 Allowable deflection limits δ_a are usually specified in design codes or can be defined by the engineer or
48 the building authorities, and can be either constant (deterministic) or considered as uncertain variables [1].
49 On the other hand, the actual deflection of the structure $\Delta(t)$ can be estimated directly from suitable
50 structural analyses. Until now, elastic analyses were customarily sufficient to determine $\Delta(t)$ when the
51 design of conventional steel structures was based on the traditional *two-step* approach adopted in current
52 international structural codes [2-4]. However, most relevant design codes for carbon steel and stainless
53 steel structures in the Australian, US and Eurocode frameworks (i.e., AS/NZS 4100 [2], AISC 360 [3],
54 AISC 370 [5], prEN 1993-1-14 [6]) already incorporate preliminary versions of new direct system-based
55 *design-by-analysis* approaches that have been developed over the last decade in response to the rapid
56 advances in design software and exponential growth in the computational power of desktop computers.

57 The Direct Design Method (DDM) is one such *design-by-analysis* methods and is based on geometric and
58 material nonlinear (advanced) finite element analyses that incorporate the effect of actual material
59 properties, geometric imperfections and residual stresses. Design recommendations for the direct design
60 of hot-rolled carbon steel frames [7-10], cold-formed steel frames [11,12], steel storage rack frames [13]
61 and steel scaffolds [14] using the DDM have been proposed in recent years, and the extension of the
62 Method to new materials and structural types is currently underway. Recommendations for the direct
63 design of stainless steel frames have been recently proposed as a result of the research works carried out
64 in the frame of the NewGeneSS project [15], which accounted for the pronounced nonlinearity of the
65 stress-strain response, the significant strain-hardening properties exhibited by stainless steel alloys, and
66 the consequent need for independent reliability calibrations [16,17]. Using the variability models
67 specifically calibrated for stainless steel member and material properties reported in [18], the reliability of
68 cold-formed stainless steel portal frames subjected to gravity loads (i.e., dead loads and imposed (live)
69 loads) and combinations of dead and wind loads at their ultimate limit state was investigated in [19,20],
70 from which the system safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and resistance factors ϕ_s reported in Table 1 were proposed for
71 the three main international design frameworks, i.e., the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks, based
72 on suitable target reliability indices.

73 Although key advantages of the structural performance of stainless steel alloys such as the
74 considerable strength reserve due to strain-hardening and the capacity to sustain large deformations
75 before reaching collapse can be fully exploited through advanced system-based design approaches,
76 these methods generally lead to potentially lighter structures and result in larger ultimate limit state
77 deformations [7]. When combined with the nonlinear behaviour exhibited by stainless steel alloys even
78 for moderate levels of strain, the larger deformations and loss of material stiffness result in more
79 significant destabilising effects and thus, greater attention is required to serviceability limit states for
80 stainless steel structures than for carbon steel structures. In fact, international design standards for
81 stainless steel structures (prEN 1993-1-4 [21], ASCE 8 [22] and AS/NZS 4673 [23]) require that the
82 effect of the nonlinear stress-strain behaviour is taken into account when estimating deflections by using
83 a reduced modulus of elasticity E_r , which is based on the secant modulus corresponding to the design
84 stress, instead of the initial Young's modulus E . This effect is implicitly taken into account in *design-*

85 *by-analysis* approaches, but does require a separate serviceability limit state check, the reliability of
86 which is investigated herein, in addition to resistance considerations.

87 This paper sets out a general framework for assessing the serviceability limit state reliability at
88 system level and presents the reliability analysis of stainless steel portal frames under gravity loads and
89 combined dead and wind load configurations. The paper introduces six baseline frames used in the
90 analysis and briefly describes the finite element models developed in Section 2, while in Section 3 target
91 reliability indices required for serviceability limit states for the three main international design
92 frameworks are presented, and suitable load combinations and stochastic models for different loading
93 types and reference periods are described. Section 4 presents the input information necessary to derive
94 reliability analyses, including statistics of the uncertain variables affecting the behaviour of stainless
95 steel frames and the resulting frame stiffness characteristics. Section 4 also describes the methodology
96 adopted in the analysis and provides an overview of the serviceability limit state criteria for portal
97 frames available in the literature. Finally, Section 5 presents and discusses the results of the
98 serviceability reliability calculations for vertical deflections under gravity loads and for lateral drifts
99 under wind loads for the three design frameworks.

100 **2. DESCRIPTION OF BASELINE FRAMES AND FINITE ELEMENT MODELS**

101 This Section briefly describes the main characteristics of the baseline frames considered in this study,
102 and provides a summary of the key features of the finite element models developed and the validation
103 thereof against experimental results.

104 **2.1. BASELINE COLD-FORMED STAINLESS STEEL FRAMES**

105 The study presented in this paper is based on six portal frames made from cold-formed stainless steel
106 rectangular hollow section (RHS) tubes, including the three most common stainless steel families. As
107 indicated in Table 2, the austenitic stainless steel grade EN 1.4301 (ASTM 304) was adopted for
108 Frames 1 and 2, while the duplex grade EN 1.4462 (ASTM 2205) was chosen for Frames 3 and 4 and
109 the ferritic grade EN 1.4003 (ASTM UNS S40977) was used for Frames 5 and 6. Frames 1, 3 and 5
110 featured RHS 150×100×4 tubes, while the cross-section adopted for Frames 2, 4 and 6 was
111 RHS 250×150×4, where the H×B×t notation indicates the cross-section height H, width B and thickness
112 t. The nominal overall frame dimensions for each frame are also reported in Table 2, including the span

113 length and the heights at eaves and at roof ridges. These baseline frames are identical to those used in
114 previous publications on ultimate limit state reliability calibrations under gravity loads [19] and
115 combined gravity plus wind load [20] cases, and the full details of the frames and their failure modes
116 can be found in these publications. For the joints at the base, apex and eave sections the stiffened welded
117 connections suitable for rigid portal frames recommended in [24] were adopted, typical examples of
118 which are shown in Figure 1. The moment–rotation curves of this type of connections can be reasonably
119 described by a bi-linear model defined by two stiffness parameters and two moment capacities [12,19],
120 the details of which are given in [19,20] for the baseline frames. Table 3 reports the nominal initial
121 stiffness values adopted at the base, apex and eave welded connections, while the values of the
122 remaining parameters can be found in [19,20]. It should be also noted that the study presented in this
123 paper assumed that the ultimate moment and ductility capacities of the joints were not reached at the
124 failure states of the frames, and thus did not consider joint failure.

125 The serviceability limit states considered in this study covered vertical deflections under gravity
126 loads (i.e., dead (G) and imposed (Q) loads) and lateral drifts due to wind (W) loads. These load cases,
127 including the wind load pattern considered, are illustrated in Figure 2 and correspond to those adopted
128 in the ultimate limit state reliability calibrations carried out in [19,20]. Since previous research works
129 [7-13,19,20] have shown that it is not possible to achieve uniform levels of reliability for different
130 imposed-to-dead load ratios, nor for different wind-to-dead load ratios, this study considered several
131 nominal imposed-to-dead load ratios $\alpha = Q_n/G_n$ for vertical deflection reliability studies, while
132 different values of design (nominal) dead loads G_n were investigated for lateral drift reliability
133 calculations. Although the imposed-to-dead load ratio α typically ranges from 0.5 to 4.0 [25], the
134 common load ratio for hollow section steel structures is $\alpha = 2.0$ [11,19], and thus imposed-to-dead load
135 ratios close to 2.0, between 1.0 and 2.5, were considered. For combined gravity plus wind load cases,
136 the effect of wind-to-dead load ratios was investigated through three values of design (nominal) dead
137 loads for each frame, namely GW1, GW2 and GW3 load scenarios, representing relatively light,
138 medium and heavy wind loads. The nominal values of the dead loads considered in this study can be
139 found in [20].

140 2.2. DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

141 System strengths and deflections of stainless steel frames were estimated from advanced numerical
142 simulations developed using the finite element (FE) software ABAQUS [26]. Frames were modelled using
143 S4R shell elements, which have been widely used in the simulation of cold-formed stainless steel members
144 [27,28] and frames [19,20,29], and a mesh size of approximately 25 mm × 25 mm was chosen from a
145 mesh convergence study, striking a suitable compromise between accuracy and computational cost. The
146 FE models included all features relevant to the response of cold-formed stainless steel portal frames,
147 including initial geometric imperfections, connection behaviour, suitable material properties and residual
148 stresses. Global initial geometric imperfections were introduced into the FE models by directly modifying
149 the position of the nodes according to the relevant out-of-plumb angle, while local and member
150 imperfections were introduced from prior linear buckling analyses, to which appropriate amplitudes
151 (extensively discussed in [19,20]) were assigned for nominal frames and structural analysis models.

152 Connections at the bases were modelled using *HINGE* type connector elements available in the
153 ABAQUS library, while for the apex and eaves connections a system of rigid *BEAM* and *UJOINT*
154 connector elements were adopted and user-defined bi-linear moment–rotation curves were assigned,
155 following the configuration described in [19]. The characteristic nonlinear stress–strain properties
156 exhibited by stainless steel alloys and their considerable strain-hardening are commonly described using
157 two-stage Ramberg-Osgood material models [30,31], which are based on basic material properties such
158 as the Young’s modulus E , the yield stress f_y , the ultimate tensile strength f_u and the corresponding
159 ultimate strain ϵ_u , as well as on the strain-hardening exponents n and m . Values (or predictive
160 expressions) for these material parameters are provided in the different structural [5,6,22,23,32] or
161 material [33] standards. Material properties were introduced into the FE models through user-defined
162 nonlinear true stress vs true plastic strain curves obtained from appropriate material parameters and the
163 two-stage Ramberg-Osgood model, while residual stresses corresponding to the model proposed in [34]
164 for cold-formed rectangular hollow sections were input using the **INITIAL CONDITIONS, TYPE-*
165 *STRESS* option. Further details of the material properties and residual stress patterns can be found in
166 [19,20].

167 In the models reproducing stainless steel frames under dead and imposed loads, gravity loads were
168 applied at the upper faces of the rafters and the geometrically and materially nonlinear analyses were
169 performed using the Static Riks method [26] until the frames collapsed. Alternatively, the behaviour of
170 the frames under combined dead and wind loads was modelled using static pushover analyses, in which
171 dead loads were first fully applied at the upper faces of the rafters followed by the wind loads introduced
172 incrementally at the rafters and columns. In this case, the analyses corresponding to the dead loading
173 increments were performed using the Static General method, while wind loading increments were
174 solved through the Static Riks method [26].

175 The finite element models were validated against the experimental results on austenitic stainless
176 steel frames reported in [29,35]. These frames featured similar joint and base connections to those
177 considered in this study and were subjected to vertical and horizontal loading conditions. It should be
178 noted that small modifications were made to the developed ABAQUS scripts to adapt them to the
179 particular characteristics of the experimental set-up, including the introduction of the loading and
180 boundary conditions, although the main considerations discussed in this Section were still valid. Full
181 details of the FE model validation can be found in [19], which indicated that the models were capable
182 of accurately replicating the behaviour of the stainless steel frames under vertical and horizontal
183 loading, as per the comparison between experimental and numerical ultimate loads, vertical load–
184 deflection curves, horizontal load–displacement paths and failure modes.

185 **3. TARGET RELIABILITY INDICES AND SERVICEABILITY LOADS**

186 This Section introduces the target reliability indices required for serviceability in the three design
187 frameworks investigated and describes the suitable load combinations and design loads to be adopted
188 in serviceability limit state checks. The Section also presents the stochastic models available in the
189 literature for the different loading types and a variety of reference periods.

190 **3.1. TARGET RELIABILITY INDICES FOR SERVICEABILITY**

191 Safety factors and resistance factors specified in different structural standards were calibrated in order
192 to meet specific target reliability indices in ultimate limit state (ULS) design, which are set out in the
193 standards along with other aspects related to the reliability framework adopted in the development of
194 the different design specifications. The minimum target reliability index recommended in prEN 1990

195 [36] for Class CC2 structures and a reference period of 50 years in ultimate limit state is $\beta_0 = 3.8$, which
196 is commonly adopted in reliability analyses carried out in the Eurocode framework, while the values
197 historically assumed for steel structures in the US and Australian frameworks range between $\beta_0 = 2.5$
198 and $\beta_0 = 3.0$ [37,38], corresponding to Risk Categories I and II structures in the ASCE 7 [39]
199 Specification for ductile failure modes. In contrast, and since safety is not generally an issue in
200 serviceability limit states (SLS), serviceability checks do not require the use of safety factors or
201 resistance factors and the reliability criteria for SLS generally results in lower prescribed target indices
202 β_0 than for ULS.

203 In prEN 1990 [36], the target reliability index for Class CC2 structures for irreversible serviceability
204 limit states is $\beta_0 = 1.50$ for a reference period of 50 years, which corresponds to an approximate annual
205 target index of $\beta_0 = 2.90$ (or an annual probability of exceedance of 0.2%). It should be noted that these
206 two β_0 values correspond to the same reliability level but to different reference periods (50 and 1 years,
207 respectively), which may or may not coincide with the design service lifetime of the structure. On the
208 other hand, the serviceability load combinations included in the Serviceability Appendix in ASCE 7
209 [39] are based on annual exceedance probabilities of around 5-10%, which correspond to target
210 reliability indices of about $\beta_0 = 1.28$ – 1.64 . Likewise, the AS/NZS 1170.0 [40] Specification defines an
211 annual probability of exceedance for serviceability limit states equal to 1/25 for wind and snow load
212 cases, which is equivalent to a target reliability index of $\beta_0 = 1.75$.

213 These β_0 values for serviceability limit states (i.e., $\beta_0 = 2.90$, $\beta_0 = 1.64$ and $\beta_0 = 1.75$ for the
214 Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks, respectively) will be used in Section 5 to evaluate the
215 reliability of stainless steel frames under gravity and combined gravity plus wind load combinations. It
216 is worth emphasizing that although the target reliability index considered for the Eurocode design
217 framework is significantly higher than those specified in the US or Australian frameworks, the
218 Eurocode index corresponds to irreversible serviceability considerations while the others refer to short-
219 term effects. These target values need to be compared with reliability indices calculated using the
220 corresponding serviceability load combinations prescribed in the different standards for serviceability,
221 which are discussed in the following Section.

222 3.2. LOAD COMBINATIONS AND DESIGN LOADS FOR SERVICEABILITY

223 International standards specify different load combinations to be adopted when checking ultimate or
224 serviceability limit states [36,39,40], and are usually based on factored nominal loads. Nominal loads
225 defined in international loading standards are traditionally based on a 50-year return period [39,41-43],
226 although some wind loading standards have recently adopted considerably higher return periods (e.g., the
227 return periods adopted in the current ASCE 7 [39] and AS/NZS 1170.2 [44] specifications are $T = 700$
228 years and $T = 500$ years, respectively). When factored according to the ultimate limit state load
229 combinations [36,39,40], design loads have significantly small probabilities of being exceeded in 50 years
230 (which is the average service lifetime of typical steel structures), and therefore it does not seem reasonable
231 to base serviceability criteria on such severe requirements [45]. Conversely, suitable loads for checking
232 deflections can be based on the assumption that the deflection limits should not be exceeded, on average,
233 more than once during a tenancy period [45] and may therefore be only a fraction of the factored nominal
234 loads. Thus, serviceability load combinations are defined using loads corresponding to lower periods of
235 reference or feature short-term and long-term combination factors.

236 prEN 1990 [36] defines three different load combinations for serviceability, namely the
237 characteristic, frequent and quasi-permanent combinations, each of which is affected by different
238 combination factors. Since the target reliability index given in prEN 1990 [36] corresponds to
239 irreversible serviceability limit states, the characteristic load combinations given by $\sum F_d = \sum G_{k,i} +$
240 $Q_{k,1} + \sum \psi_{0,j} Q_{k,j}$ was adopted in this study, where $\sum F_d$ is the total service design load, $G_{k,i}$ are the
241 characteristic permanent actions, $Q_{k,1}$ is the characteristic leading variable action, $Q_{k,j}$ represent the
242 accompanying characteristic variable actions and $\psi_{0,j}$ are the combination factors. Since load cases
243 investigated in this paper correspond to a permanent (dead) action G_k acting in combination with one
244 single variable action (imposed load Q_k or wind load W_k), characteristic load combinations for
245 serviceability can be simplified to $\sum F_d = G_k + Q_k$ and $\sum F_d = G_k + W_k$. On the contrary, target
246 reliabilities for serviceability in ASCE 7 [39] refer to short-term effects, which for the load cases
247 investigated in this paper result in $\sum F_d = D_n + L_n$ and $\sum F_d = D_n + W_a$, where D_n and L_n are the
248 nominal dead load and imposed loads, respectively, and W_a refers to the wind load corresponding to

249 the serviceability wind speed (10-year mean recurrence interval for typical buildings). Since according
250 to [10,11,46] 10-year wind loads can be obtained by multiplying the 50-year wind loads by a conversion
251 factor of 0.7, the wind design load $W_a = 0.7W_{n,50}$ was adopted in this study for the US design
252 framework. Finally, load combinations prescribed in the AS/NZS 1170.0 [40] Specification for
253 serviceability limit states are based on the nominal permanent loads G_n , the short-term variable loads
254 $\psi_s Q_n$ and the serviceability wind load W_s , based on a wind speed corresponding to the annual
255 probability of exceedance for serviceability. The short-term factor for imposed actions in
256 AS/NZS 1170.0 [40] is $\psi_s = 0.70$ for roofs and most common floor uses, and thus the load
257 combinations adopted in this study for the Australian framework were $\sum F_d = G_n + \psi_s Q_n$ and $\sum F_d =$
258 $G_n + W_s$, where $\psi_s = 0.70$.

259 3.3. STOCHASTIC MODELS FOR SERVICEABILITY LOADS

260 When serviceability limit states are evaluated from a probabilistic point of view, the definition of
261 stochastic models accounting for the variability of the structural loads involved and the selection of
262 suitable periods of reference is fundamental. Since the target reliability indices described in Section 3.1
263 are based on annual probabilities of exceedance, it might seem reasonable to adopt a reference period
264 of 1 year for reliability calculations. However, the load models reported in the literature for imposed
265 and wind loads for reference periods shorter than the usual 50-year period do not always include annual
266 reference periods. Load models available in the literature for short reference periods generally
267 correspond to the mean duration of typical tenancies, which range between 8 years and 10 years for
268 buildings [45,47,48], and thus these periods have been adopted in this paper: 8 years for vertical
269 deflection serviceability limit states under gravity loads and 10 years for lateral drift serviceability under
270 wind loads, in line with the availability of stochastic models for loads and previous studies [8,11,45,49].
271 Nevertheless, the reliabilities corresponding to a reference period of 1 year have been estimated in all
272 cases to allow a direct comparison between load cases and with the annual target reliability indices
273 prescribed in the different design frameworks.

274 Probabilistic models for the loads corresponding to several reference periods (8 years, 10 years and
275 50 years), based on the nominal loads for different return periods ($T = 50$ years, $T = 500$ years and

276 T =700 years) are reported in Table 4 for the dead loads (G or D), imposed loads (Q or L) and wind
277 loads (W). Note that the wind loads assumed in this paper correspond to ordinary winds, limited to the
278 regions not affected by tropical cyclones. Mean values (as fractions of the code-specified nominal
279 values), coefficients of variation (COV) and distribution types are provided for the Eurocode [19,20],
280 US [25,51,52] and Australian [12,19,53] frameworks. These values were obtained from the literature,
281 as indicated, or estimated from the models available when no information was directly available, as
282 described below. From the load model proposed in [52] for imposed loads in the US framework and an
283 8-year reference period, the equivalent models for the Eurocode and Australian frameworks were
284 estimated assuming that the factors by which the mean imposed loads are reduced from a 50-year
285 reference period to a 8-year reference period were the same for the three design frameworks. Therefore,
286 using the statistics for reference periods of 50 years reported in Table 4, mean values of the maximum
287 imposed loads for an 8-year reference period equal to $0.52 \cdot Q_k$ and $0.65 \cdot Q_n$ were adopted for the
288 Eurocode and Australian frameworks, respectively, with the same COVs.

289 Regarding the wind loads, stochastic models corresponding to a reference period of 10 years were
290 assumed for the three design frameworks, in line with recent serviceability reliability studies on steel
291 frames designed by direct analysis [8,11]. These studies assumed an average factor of 1.45 to relate the
292 maximum wind loads corresponding to reference periods of 50 years and 10 years, and adopted a
293 coefficient of variation of 0.50 for the 10-year reference period wind loads. Using the wind load model
294 reported in [25] for a reference period of 50 years and the 1.45 factor, a mean maximum wind load of
295 $0.51 \cdot W_{n,50}$ can be obtained for the US framework and a reference period of 10 years, as reported in
296 Table 4. Since no stochastic models are available in the literature for the Eurocode and the Australian
297 frameworks for reference periods equivalent to the mean duration of tenancies, a similar approach to
298 that adopted for the US framework was assumed. Accepting that the factor by which the mean maximum
299 wind loads are reduced from a 50-year reference period to a 10-year period are the same for the three
300 frameworks, and using the wind load statistics proposed in [20] and [53] for reference periods of
301 50 years (see Table 4), stochastic wind load models with mean values of $0.49 \cdot W_k$ and $0.47 \cdot W_{n,50}$ can

302 be adopted for the 10-year reference period wind loads in the Eurocode and Australian framework,
303 respectively, with a COV of 0.50.

304 Note that while the characteristic wind loads W_k prescribed in EN 1991-1-4 [42] correspond to a
305 return period of 50 years, the nominal loads specified in the latest versions of the ASCE 7 [39] and
306 AS/NZS 1170.2 [44] specifications correspond to return periods of $T = 700$ years (denoted by $W_{n,700}$)
307 and $T = 500$ years (denoted by $W_{n,500}$), respectively. Since wind load models reported in the literature
308 are traditionally referred to the nominal loads corresponding to return periods of $T = 50$ years, they need
309 to be updated to adhere to the revised nominal wind loads. This can be done using the approximate
310 relationship between the wind loads for a T -year return period W_T and the wind load for a 50-year return
311 period W_{50} given in Eq. 2 [25], which is valid for most of the non-hurricane-prone regions of the US
312 [39]. Eq. 2 results in a $W_{n,700}/W_{n,50} = 1.60$ ratio for the US framework, which leads to a mean
313 maximum wind load of $0.33 \cdot W_{n,700}$ for a wind load corresponding to a 10-year reference period, as
314 reported in Table 4. In the absence of a specific equation for Australian non-hurricane regions, Eq. 2
315 has been adopted in this study to estimate the $W_{n,500}/W_{n,50}$ ratio for the Australian framework, which
316 results in a mean maximum wind load of $0.32 \cdot W_{n,500}$ for a reference period of 10 years.

$$W_T = W_{50}[0.36 + 0.10\ln(12T)]^2 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

317
318 It should be emphasized that, in addition to the stochastic models for wind loads, it is also necessary to
319 update the design wind loads discussed in Section 3.2 for the US and Australian design frameworks to
320 convert these loads to the nominal wind load based on 700-year and 500-year return periods.
321 Considering that the serviceability wind load is $0.7 \cdot W_{n,50}$, and using Eq. 2, the service loads result in
322 $0.44W_{n,700}$ for the US framework and in $0.46W_{n,500}$ for the Australian framework.

323 In the reliability analyses carried out in this paper, the statistics corresponding to 8-year reference
324 periods reported in Table 4 were used for imposed loads in conjunction with the load combinations
325 described in Section 3.2 for the analysis of vertical deflections under gravity loads. For the reliability
326 assessment of lateral drifts under wind loading, the load models corresponding to 10-year reference
327 periods and design loads referred to the W_k , $W_{n,700}$ and $W_{n,500}$ nominal wind loads were adopted for
328 the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks, respectively.

329 **4. RELIABILITY ANALYSIS FOR SERVICEABILITY LIMIT STATE**

330 This Section presents the input information necessary to perform the serviceability reliability analyses
331 of stainless steel frames under different loading configurations. The statistics of the random variables
332 affecting the response of stainless steel structures are described first, followed by the methodology
333 adopted in the reliability study. Subsequently, the Section provides an overview of the serviceability
334 limit state criteria available in the literature for portal frames and describes the procedure adopted in the
335 derivation of suitable stochastic models for frame flexibility.

336 4.1. UNCERTAIN VARIABLES AFFECTING THE BEHAVIOUR OF FRAMES

337 Numerical models representing the nominal frames investigated in this paper were built following the
338 material properties, residual stresses, initial geometric imperfections, connection behaviour and loading
339 patterns prescribed in the prEN 1993-1-14 [6], AISC 370 [5] and AS/NZS 4100 [2] specifications for
340 the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks, respectively. However, the determination of suitable
341 stochastic distributions for system strength and stiffness of actual stainless steel frames under different
342 loading configurations is fundamental to the calculation of reliability indices in ultimate and
343 serviceability limit states. For this, extensive numerical simulations accounting for the variability of all
344 the variables affecting the behaviour of stainless steel frames were carried out in [19,20], based on the
345 finite element model described in Section 2.2.

346 The statistical distributions adopted in the study for cross-section geometric properties, material
347 properties, imperfections (at frame, member and local levels), residual stresses and connection
348 behaviour were based on the probabilistic models proposed in [18] for stainless steel structural
349 members, as well as in previous reliability studies on cold-formed steel portal frames [12] when
350 available measurements were insufficient to derive specific stochastic models for stainless steel
351 structures. Details of these statistical distributions, in addition to the correlations assumed for the
352 different random variables, can be found in [18-20]. In addition to these variables, system strength and
353 stiffness values included the effect of model uncertainty accounting for the assumptions and
354 approximations made when using advanced FE simulations. Since it was not possible to derive a
355 specific probabilistic characterization of the model uncertainty from the comparison between the
356 numerical and experimental results of stainless steel frames due to the limited number of specimens

357 available, an unbiased log-normal distribution with a COV of 0.05 was adopted in this study, as
358 recommended in the literature [48,50].

359 4.2. SERVICEABILITY RELIABILITY ANALYSIS METHOD

360 With the aim of assessing the reliability of stainless steel frames designed using the DDM provisions
361 proposed in [19,20] in serviceability limit states, the probability of failure P_f (i.e., the probability of
362 actual deflections in the structures exceeding specified allowable deflection limitations) of the six
363 baseline frames under different loading scenarios was estimated in this study. The probability of failure
364 can be evaluated using direct Monte Carlo simulations, which was the approach followed in previous
365 reliability studies in the context of the DDM [8,11], but such methodology requires that approximately
366 10,000 simulations be carried out in order to accurately estimate P_f for serviceability limit states. Since
367 the computational effort to perform this number of simulations is prohibitive when these are based on
368 nonlinear shell-finite element analyses, more efficient reliability analysis methods need to be adopted.

369 The study presented in this paper was based on the methodology proposed in [45], in which
370 reliability indices β were calculated based on First-Order Reliability Methods (FORM). According to
371 [45], the limit state function for serviceability considerations given in Eq. 1 can be re-written as $g =$
372 $\delta_a - K \cdot F$, where δ_a is the allowable deflection, K is the stiffness of the structure and F is the load
373 considered, from which the probability of failure can be calculated as $P_f = P(g \leq 0)$, since $g \leq 0$
374 defines the failure domain. In the case of stainless steel frames subjected to gravity loads only, K
375 corresponds to the vertical stiffness of the frame at the apex joint K_v and F represents the total gravity
376 load, including dead G (or permanent) and imposed Q loads. Conversely, when the reliability of frames
377 under combined gravity plus wind loads is investigated, K is the lateral stiffness of the frame K_w and F
378 is the wind load W . Values of allowable deflections δ_a are discussed in Section 4.3 and depend on the
379 load case: while δ_a corresponds to the vertical apex deflection $\delta_{a,v}$ when gravity load scenarios are
380 considered, it refers to the lateral drift $\delta_{a,w}$ when dead plus wind load cases are investigated. The
381 procedure to compute the probability of failure of each frame has been extensively reported in the
382 literature [7-14,19,20,45], and thus only a summary of the main steps is provided in this Section.

- 383 (1) Determine the probabilistic models (distribution type and parameters) for the system stiffnesses
384 K_v and K_w under gravity and wind loads, respectively, based on the advanced finite element
385 models accounting for all relevant uncertainties carried out in [19,20]. Through the adoption of
386 Latin-Hypercube sampling (LHS) techniques, the number of required simulations was reduced to
387 200 cases per frame and load case. This is further discussed in Section 4.4.
- 388 (2) At their limit state, nominal frames must satisfy $\delta_{a,v} = K_{v,n}(\gamma_G G_n + \gamma_Q Q_n)$ or $\delta_{a,w} =$
389 $K_{w,n}(\gamma_W W_n)$ for the vertical deflection and lateral drift checks, respectively, using the nominal
390 stiffnesses ($K_{v,n}$ and $K_{w,n}$), appropriate load combinations (i.e., γ_G , γ_Q and γ_W factors for dead,
391 imposed and wind loads prescribed in prEN 1990 [36], ASCE 7 [39] and AS/NZS 1170.0 [40])
392 and design loads for the different design frameworks, as discussed in Section 3.2. Note that the
393 lateral drifts caused by the dead loads were neglected in combined gravity plus wind load cases
394 since the FE simulations from Step (1) showed that they represented less than 5% of the total lateral
395 drift values obtained for the service loads. Note also that serviceability limit state checks do not
396 require the use of safety factors or resistance factors.
- 397 (3) Define the relationship between the nominal stiffnesses $K_{v,n}$ or $K_{w,n}$ and the loads through the
398 Load Scale Method and the design equations introduced in Step (2) [13]. Using the imposed-to-
399 dead load ratio $\alpha = Q_n/G_n$ for gravity loads, the nominal loads G_n , Q_n and W_n can be re-written
400 in terms of the nominal stiffness values as per in Eq. 3 and Eq. 4 for the gravity load and wind load
401 cases, respectively.

$$G_n = \frac{\delta_{a,v}}{K_{v,n}(\gamma_G + \gamma_Q \alpha)} \text{ and } Q_n = \frac{\alpha \delta_{a,v}}{K_{v,n}(\gamma_G + \gamma_Q \alpha)} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$W_n = \frac{\delta_{a,w}}{K_{w,n} \gamma_W} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

- 402
403 (4) Re-define the probabilistic models for the different loads from the relationships established in
404 Step (3) and the models available in the literature and discussed in Section 3.3 (see Table 4).
- 405 (5) Compute the reliability index β based on FORM techniques [1,45] using MATLAB [54]. The
406 reliability index is related to the probability of failure P_f through $\beta = \Phi^{-1}(1 - P_f)$, where Φ^{-1} is
407 the inverse standard normal distribution function.

408 Using the steps described above in conjunction with the load combinations (i.e., γ_i factors) and design
409 loads specified in the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks, reliability indices β can be
410 computed for each imposed-to-dead load ratio α and for each of the three levels of dead load
411 investigated. These β -values can be then compared with the target values β_0 discussed in Section 3.1
412 for the six baseline frames, which is addressed in Section 5.

413 4.3. SERVICEABILITY LIMIT STATE CRITERIA

414 Serviceability limit states are generally defined in terms of (i) excessive deflections or rotations that can
415 affect the appearance or functionality of structures or damage secondary elements, and (ii) excessive
416 vibrations that may cause discomfort to users or affect the performance of equipment. In this study only
417 vertical deflections of the roof elements due to gravity loads and lateral drifts caused by wind loading
418 were considered. Based on the historical record of structures with a satisfactory service performance, it
419 is generally assumed that the serviceability demands of structures can be met by limiting the deflections
420 to certain commonly accepted allowable values [45]. Precise points or limits at which a structure is
421 deemed unserviceable are difficult to determine, since they depend on the perception of the occupants
422 and the nature of the structure under study, and thus the definition of these allowable deflection criteria
423 δ_a has been a subject of study in recent decades [1]. The limits are usually considered to be deterministic
424 (or constant), but since they are sometimes associated with subjective human reactions, they have also
425 been assumed as random in some studies [55]. International design standards and other design guides
426 for specific structural typologies recommend limits for allowable deflections for a variety of structural
427 members and different load cases, but these limits show considerable variability. Table 5 presents a
428 comparison of different allowable serviceability criteria for steel structures in terms of vertical
429 deflection limits at the apex sections $\delta_{a,v}$ and lateral drift limitations at the eaves $\delta_{a,w}$ found in different
430 international standards [36,39,40,56,57], design guides [58-60] and recent research works investigating
431 the reliability of steel structures in serviceability limit states [8,11,49]. Different limitations exist
432 depending on the structure type (single storey building, portal frame), type of supported material (metal
433 cladding, masonry cladding), occupancy, type of roof (accessible, not accessible) and loading type
434 (dead, imposed, wind or total loads), and are subject to the judgment of the designer, among others. The

435 overview presented in Table 5 includes allowable serviceability criteria relevant to the investigated
436 frames only.

437 From the vertical deflection limitations reported in Table 5 it is evident that a significant variation
438 exists in the recommended allowable deflection limits $\delta_{a,v}$. The values specified in prEN 1990 [36] for
439 not-accessible and accessible resilient roofing are $s/125$ and $s/250$, respectively, where s is the span
440 of the frame or horizontal element, while the ASCE 7 [39] and AS/NZS 1170.0 [40] specifications
441 recommend limiting values equal to $s/240$ and $s/300$ under imposed loads and long-term gravity loads,
442 respectively. In general, limiting vertical deflection $\delta_{a,v}$ values for apex sections lie around $s/250$ under
443 imposed loads only and around $s/150$ under total gravity loads. Regarding the lateral drifts at eaves
444 $\delta_{a,w}$, Table 5 shows that limitations typically range between $H_1/500$ and $H_1/150$, where H_1 is the
445 height of the frame at the eaves. These drift limits are of about the same magnitude as the erection
446 tolerances prescribed in different international standards [61,62]. Based on these considerations and the
447 serviceability limit state criteria adopted in previous studies, the reliability analyses presented in this
448 paper were premised on the assumption that allowable deflection limits were deterministic, and the
449 limits adopted corresponded to $s/150$ for the vertical deflection of the apex section under total gravity
450 loads and $H_1/300$ for the lateral drift of the frame at the eaves under wind loads, which is at the upper
451 limit of what is customarily used by most design offices [8,11]. However, it should be noted that the
452 reliability index is independent of the allowable deflection criteria δ_a adopted in the analysis, and that β
453 only depends on the assumed load statistics, as highlighted in [45]. This is because the adopted
454 serviceability reliability analysis method, as described in Step (2) of Section 4.2, considers that the
455 structure deflects precisely to δ_a under the nominal loads. Since it is necessary to assume certain values
456 of the allowable deflection criteria δ_a to carry out the analysis, limits equal to $s/150$ and $H_1/300$ have
457 been adopted in this paper for vertical deflections and lateral drifts. The results would be, however,
458 identical if alternative allowable deflection criteria δ_a were adopted for the analysis.

459 4.4. STOCHASTIC MODELS FOR FRAME STIFFNESS

460 The fundamental input information required when deriving reliability indices through First-Order
461 Reliability Methods (FORM) are the probabilistic models for the different random variables involved

462 in the limit state function $g(\cdot)$ adopted. While the models for gravity and wind loads have been already
463 discussed in Section 3.3, and allowable deflections were considered as deterministic in this study,
464 suitable stochastic models for frame vertical K_v and lateral stiffnesses K_w are required, as per in Step (1)
465 of Section 4.2. Although Galambos and Ellingwood [45] demonstrated that reliability indices were
466 essentially the same when the stiffness of structures was considered to be random or deterministic in
467 serviceability studies, results reported in [45] also evidenced that neglecting the variability of the
468 stiffness leads to higher (i.e., less conservative) β -values. Moreover, nonlinear material properties might
469 cause an additional loss of stiffness in stainless steel structures that does not occur in carbon steel frames
470 and might further affect the calculated β -values. Therefore, this study considered the vertical and lateral
471 stiffness of the frames as random variables. With the aim of determining suitable stochastic models for
472 the flexibility of stainless steel frames, the load-deflection (or load-drift) curves corresponding to the
473 simulations carried out in [19,20], which represented real frames with random properties, were used.

474 Structures affected by geometrical and material nonlinearities result in nonlinear load-displacement
475 curves, and thus, the stiffness of these structures depends on the load level under consideration and is
476 generally lower than the initial stiffness (i.e., the stiffness of the structure while it behaves elastically). In
477 such cases, the total vertical deflection d_{tot} (or lateral drift) can be considered as the sum of an elastic
478 deflection d_{el} , governed by the initial stiffness of the frame, and a plastic deflection d_{pl} that represents
479 the additional deflection caused by the loss of stiffness due to the nonlinear geometrical or material
480 characteristics of the structure, as shown in Figure 3; and both components of the total deflection will
481 typically show certain levels of variability. The variability of the elastic deflection occurs primarily as a
482 result of the random nature of the Young's modulus E and the initial stiffness of the connections at the
483 frame joints, while the variability in d_{pl} is due to the randomness of the yield stress f_y and the strain-
484 hardening exponent n . By determining the variability of these two components, stochastic models can be
485 derived for the vertical K_v and lateral stiffness K_w of the baseline frames investigated.

486 To characterize the variability of the elastic component of the deflection d_{el} , the initial stiffness of
487 each of the simulated frames was computed from the vertical load-apex deflection curves (denoted as
488 $K_{v,0}$) and the wind load-lateral drift curves (denoted as $K_{w,0}$). The statistics of the calculated initial

489 stiffness values are reported in Table 6, where $\bar{K}_{v,0}$ and $\bar{K}_{w,0}$ are the mean values of the initial vertical
490 and lateral stiffnesses, and $V_{K_{v,0}}$ and $V_{K_{w,0}}$ represent the corresponding coefficients of variation.
491 Individual values of $K_{v,0}$ and $K_{w,0}$ were used to build histograms for each frame and load case, to which
492 suitable probabilistic distributions were fitted. In all cases, log-normal distributions were adjusted using
493 the Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox in MATLAB [54], based on the maximum likelihood
494 method. Figure 4 shows typical examples of the histograms built from the initial stiffness results $K_{v,0}$
495 for frames subjected to gravity loads, while Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the histograms for the initial
496 lateral stiffness $K_{w,0}$ for the GW1 and GW3 dead and wind load cases, respectively, and the fitted log-
497 normal distributions. It should be noted that whereas for most baseline frames heavy wind load
498 combinations (GW3) result in slightly higher mean lateral stiffness values than for light wind load
499 combinations (GW1), an inverse trend is observed for Frames 1 and 3 in Table 6. This apparent
500 inconsistency in mean $K_{w,0}$ values is due to the skewness of the histograms. While the mean lateral
501 stiffness values obtained from the raw data were very similar for each baseline frame regardless the
502 assumed wind load combination, the values reported in Table 6 correspond to the log-normal functions
503 used to fit the histograms, which are affected by their skewness and thus result in values that are
504 different from the mean values obtained from the raw data. Since the mean value of the fitted
505 distribution is dependent on the skewness of the histograms, which has greater associated randomness
506 than the mean value, it leads to the observed inconsistencies in the variation of $K_{w,0}$ shown in Table 6.

507 In order to evaluate the plastic component of the deflection d_{pl} due to the nonlinear stress-strain
508 behaviour of stainless steel alloys, deviations of the actual total deflections from the purely elastic
509 components d_{el} were evaluated for the service design loads. Since three design frameworks prescribing
510 different nominal loads were considered in the analysis, service design loads adopted in this paper were
511 back-calculated from the nominal FE models assuming that the frames were designed at their ultimate
512 limit state using the DDM through the following procedure. The maximum design gravity loads and
513 wind loads that each frame could endure were determined from the load factors specified in prEN 1990
514 [36], ASCE 7 [39] and AS/NZS 1170.0 [40] and the ultimate nominal frame strengths using the system
515 safety or resistance factors recommended in [19,20] for each load case. For example, the maximum

516 design gravity load in the Eurocode framework was estimated from the ULS-LRFD equation
517 $R_{k,v}/\gamma_{M,s} = 1.35G_k + 1.5Q_k$, where $R_{k,v}$ is the characteristic resistance of the frame under gravity
518 loads and $\gamma_{M,s}$ is the system safety factor recommended for gravity loads, $\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15$ (see Table 1).
519 Assuming the common $Q_k/G_k = 2$ load ratio for hollow section steel structures [11], the relationships
520 $R_{k,v} = 2.5Q_k$ and $Q_k = R_{k,v}/2.5$ were derived. Since the gravity service design load $F_{d,SLS}$ for a Q_k/G_k
521 ratio of 2 is $F_{d,SLS} = G_k + Q_k = 1.5Q_k$, the relationship between $F_{d,SLS}$ and $R_{k,v}$ was established as
522 $F_{d,SLS} = R_{k,v}/1.7$. Following a similar approach, the design wind load for serviceability in the
523 Eurocode framework was estimated from $W_{d,SLS} = R_{k,w}/(1.5\gamma_{M,s})$, which results in $W_{d,SLS} =$
524 $R_{k,w}/1.8$ if the recommended $\gamma_{M,s}$ factor of 1.20 is adopted (see Table 1), where $R_{k,w}$ is the
525 characteristic resistances of the frame under combined gravity and wind loads. Through this procedure,
526 similar design loads were obtained for the US and Australian frameworks, which represent upper
527 bounds to the serviceability design loads [63].

528 Table 7 presents the comparison between the elastic deflections $d_{v,el}$ and drifts $d_{w,el}$ with the
529 corresponding actual total deflections $d_{v,tot}$ and drifts $d_{w,tot}$ estimated from the nonlinear load-
530 deflection curves of the random frame simulations at the SLS design loads $F_{d,SLS}$ and $W_{d,SLS}$, including
531 results for the different load scenarios and the six baseline frames. The mean values and coefficients of
532 variation corresponding to the elastic-to-total deflection (or drift) ratios $d_{v,el}/d_{v,tot}$ and $d_{w,el}/d_{w,tot}$
533 reported in Table 7 indicate that the stainless steel frames investigated in this paper, when designed
534 using the DDM and the $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s factors recommended in [19,20], remain basically in the elastic
535 range for the serviceability design loads. However, the actual total deflections were found to be
536 consistently higher than those estimated elastically (i.e., all $d_{v,el}/d_{v,tot}$ and $d_{w,el}/d_{w,tot}$ ratios are below
537 unity), and thus the information in Table 7 was used to modify the statistical data reported in Table 6
538 for the initial stiffness of the frames and to derive suitable stochastic models that also account for plastic
539 deflections due to material nonlinearities.

540 Specifically, the mean values for the final stiffness distributions adopted in this study were estimated
541 by reducing the $\bar{K}_{v,0}$ and $\bar{K}_{w,0}$ values reported in Table 6 by the corresponding average $d_{v,el}/d_{v,tot}$ and
542 $d_{w,el}/d_{w,tot}$ ratios shown in Table 7, while the final coefficients of variation $V_{K,v}$ and $V_{K,w}$ were

543 calculated as the sum of the respective COV values in Table 6 and Table 7 for each load case. Log-
544 normal distributions were adopted for the final stiffness distributions, since all affecting variables (i.e.,
545 initial stiffness, yield stress and strain-hardening exponent) follow log-normal distributions [18]. The
546 mean values (\bar{K}_v and \bar{K}_w) and coefficients of variation ($V_{K,v}$ and $V_{K,w}$) of the final frame stiffness
547 distributions adopted in the reliability analyses are reported in Table 8 and Table 9 for the gravity and
548 the combined gravity plus wind load cases, respectively. The tables also include the nominal stiffness
549 values ($K_{v,n}$ and $K_{w,n}$) corresponding to the design (nominal) FE models developed following the
550 requirements of the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks. Since the six nominal baseline frames
551 exhibited a linear behaviour for the SLS design loads $F_{d,SLS}$ and $W_{d,SLS}$, the nominal stiffness values
552 adopted in the reliability studies corresponded to the nominal initial stiffnesses (i.e., $K_{v,n} = K_{v,n,0}$ and
553 $K_{w,n} = K_{w,n,0}$).

554 **5. RELIABILITY ANALYSIS RESULTS FOR SERVICEABILITY**

555 This Section presents the serviceability reliability results for stainless steel frames in the Eurocode, US
556 and Australian frameworks. The calculated reliability indices correspond to vertical deflections under
557 gravity loads and lateral drifts under wind loads. Presented separately, they are compared with the
558 relevant target reliability indices for the different design frameworks and with the results reported in
559 previous reliability studies.

560 **5.1. RELIABILITY OF VERTICAL DEFLECTIONS UNDER GRAVITY LOADS**

561 Based on the K_v stiffness variability data reported in Section 4.4 and the stochastic models for dead and
562 imposed loads reported in Table 4, this Section presents the reliability indices corresponding to the
563 serviceability limit state of the vertical deflection. Following the procedure described in Section 4.2,
564 reliability indices corresponding to the range of imposed-to-dead load ratios α considered (i.e., α ratios
565 between 1.0 and 2.5) were derived for the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks. The results showed
566 that the reliability indices β calibrated for each of the six frames were very similar for the investigated
567 range of imposed-to-dead load ratios for all design frameworks, with the largest observed differences
568 in β between $\alpha = 1.0$ and $\alpha = 2.5$ being less than 5%. Consequently, and considering that the common
569 load ratio for hollow section steel structures is $\alpha = 2.0$ [11], only the reliability indices β corresponding

570 to an imposed-to-dead load ratio of $\alpha = 2.0$ are reported in this paper. The β indices derived for stainless
571 steel frames under gravity loads corresponding to a reference period of 8 years $\beta_{8\text{yrs}}$ are reported in
572 Table 8 for the six baseline frames and the three design frameworks investigated. Since target reliability
573 indices β_0 for serviceability are generally referred to annual failure probabilities, as discussed in
574 Section 3.1, reliability indices corresponding to a reference period of 1 year, denoted by $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$, are also
575 provided in Table 8. Annual reliability indices can be estimated from the corresponding $\beta_{8\text{yrs}}$ values
576 using Eq. 5 and Eq. 6, as indicated in [8].

$$P_{f,1\text{yr}} = 1 - \sqrt[t]{1 - P_{f,t}} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$\beta_{1\text{yr}} = \Phi^{-1}(1 - P_{f,1\text{yr}}) \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

577 The annual reliability indices reported in Table 8 show that the highest $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$ values correspond to the
578 Eurocode framework, owing to the lowest mean-to-nominal imposed load ratios adopted by this
579 framework (see Table 4), which means that the nominal imposed loads in EN 1991-1-1 [41] are in general
580 more conservative than the equivalent loads prescribed in ASCE 7 [39] and AS/NZS 1170.1 [43].
581 Conversely, the $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$ values derived for the US and Australian frameworks are similar because they use
582 imposed load models with the same mean-to-nominal values. The small differences observed between the
583 US and Australian frameworks can be explained by the short-term factor ψ_s adopted by the
584 AS/NZS 1170.1 [43] Specification in the serviceability load combination, as discussed in Section 3.2,
585 resulting in slightly lower reliability indices since the adopted design load is less conservative. These
586 results are in line with the β -values calibrated for the same stainless steel frames for the gravity load
587 ultimate limit state in [19]. The average annual reliability indices $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$ considering the six baseline frames
588 are 3.19, 2.56 and 2.53 for the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks, respectively, as reported in Table
589 8, which correspond to average annual probabilities of exceedance of approximately 0.1%, 0.5% and
590 0.6%. These $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$ values should be compared with the corresponding annual target reliability indices
591 introduced in Section 3.1, which are $\beta_0 = 2.90$ for the Eurocode design framework, and $\beta_0 = 1.64$ and
592 $\beta_0 = 1.75$ for the US and the Australian frameworks, respectively. According to these values, the

594 calculated reliability indices are above the target values for the vertical deflection serviceability designs
595 for the three design frameworks, particularly for the US and Australian frameworks.

596 The reliability indices presented in Table 8 are comparable to the β -values reported in previous
597 studies investigating the reliability of steel structures in serviceability limit states under gravity loads:
598 Galambos and Ellingwood [45] reported average values of reliability indices $\beta_{8yr} = 1.86$ and
599 $\beta_{1yr} = 3.08$ for vertical deflections for periods of reference equal to 8 years and 1 year, respectively,
600 while an average annual reliability index of $\beta_{1yr} = 3.10$ was obtained by Ellingwood [49] for beams
601 loaded with gravity loads. The values in Table 8 also show that the reliability indices for serviceability
602 on an annual basis are comparable to the β -values on a 50-year basis for the ultimate limit state reported
603 in [19], as previously highlighted in [49]. It is also worth mentioning that the differences observed
604 between the annual serviceability reliability indices and the 50-year ultimate limit state reliability
605 indices are more significant for stainless steel structures than for carbon steel structures, because the
606 ultimate limit state β -values for stainless steel frames are affected by the considerably higher strength
607 reserve (i.e., mean-to-nominal frame resistance) existing in these frames due to the higher mean-to-
608 nominal yield stress ratios, a reserve that does not affect serviceability limit states and corresponding
609 reliability indices [19].

610 5.2. RELIABILITY OF LATERAL DRIFTS UNDER COMBINED GRAVITY AND WIND LOADS

611 Following a similar approach to that described for vertical deflections under gravity loads, this Section
612 presents the serviceability reliability results for stainless steel frames under combined gravity and wind
613 loads. Reliability indices corresponding to periods of reference equal to 10 years and 1 year (denoted
614 as β_{10yrs} and β_{1yr} , respectively) were calculated for the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks using
615 the methodology described in Section 4.2, the wind load models reported in Table 4 and the lateral
616 stiffness K_w variability data derived in Section 4.4. Although reliability studies were carried out
617 separately for the three levels of dead load considered in the analysis (load cases GW1, GW2 and GW3),
618 the results demonstrated that the wind-to-dead load ratio had a negligible effect on the serviceability
619 reliability evaluation of stainless steel frames, with differences in the calculated β -values being less
620 than 2% for all design frameworks. Consequently, and following the approach adopted for the

621 assessment vertical deflections, only reliability indices β corresponding to the dead load case GW1,
622 showing the lowest β -values, are reported in this paper.

623 Reliability indices derived for the serviceability limit state of stainless steel frames under combined
624 dead and wind loads (load case GW1) corresponding to a reference period of 10 years $\beta_{10\text{yrs}}$ for the six
625 baseline frames are reported in Table 9. Results corresponding to a reference period of 1 year $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$,
626 estimated using the expressions given in Eq. 5 and Eq. 6, are also included for a direct comparison with
627 the target reliability indices β_0 for serviceability. It should be noticed that the annual β -values calculated
628 for the roof drift limit state are generally lower than those reported in Table 8 for the vertical deflection
629 limit state, which is in line with the reliability indices obtained for the same frames in [19,20] when
630 assessing ultimate limit states. The annual reliability indices reported in Table 9 indicate that, consistent
631 with the results exposed in the previous Section for serviceability considerations under gravity loads,
632 the highest $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$ values for lateral drift serviceability correspond to the Eurocode framework, while the
633 reliability indices calculated for the US and Australian frameworks are very similar. This difference can
634 be explained by the different load combinations or service wind loads adopted in the three design
635 frameworks, as discussed in Section 3.2, since the load combination specified in prEN 1990 [36] adopts
636 a service load equal to the characteristic wind load defined in EN 1991-1-4 [42], corresponding to a
637 return period of 50 years, while the service loads used in the US and Australian frameworks correspond
638 to lower return periods. Average annual reliability indices $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$ for the six baseline frames and the dead
639 load case GW1 are, as reported in Table 9, 2.70, 2.01 and 2.12 for the Eurocode, US and Australian
640 frameworks, respectively, which correspond to the approximate average annual probabilities of
641 exceedance of 0.3%, 2.2% and 1.7%. Comparing these $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$ values with the target values introduced in
642 Section 3.1, it can be seen that the reliability of wind drift appears to be adequate for the US and
643 Australian design frameworks, since the calculated average $\beta_{1\text{yr}}$ values lie above the corresponding
644 target values β_0 , and that the average value obtained for the Eurocode framework is also very close to
645 the target reliability index of 2.90.

646 The reliability associated with excessive lateral drifts under wind loads has been previously
647 investigated in different studies of steel frames, in which the average annual reliability index of

648 $\beta_{1yr} = 3.29$ was reported by Galambos and Ellingwood [45] for lateral drift limit states, while a similar
649 study by Ellingwood [49] reported an average value of $\beta_{1yr} = 3.40$. These two studies conservatively
650 assumed a serviceability wind load corresponding to a 50-year return period, which is equivalent to the
651 characteristic load combination prescribed in prEN 1990 [36] for irreversible serviceability checks, and
652 thus the annual reliability indices obtained in [45,49] are comparable to the values reported in Table 9
653 for the Eurocode framework. It should be noted, however, that the β_{1yr} values reported in [45,49] are
654 slightly higher than those obtained in this study because this paper conservatively includes the effect of
655 the variability in frame stiffness, resulting in lower reliability indices. In contrast, recent studies
656 developed in the frame of the Direct Design Method that reported reliability results for serviceability
657 limit states under wind loads [8,11] found that the average values of the annual reliability indices were
658 $\beta_{1yr} = 1.86$ and $\beta_{1yr} = 1.88$ for hot-rolled and cold-formed steel frames, respectively. These values are
659 similar to the reliability indices reported for lateral drifts in Table 9 for the US and Australian
660 frameworks. The small differences observed in the annual reliability indices are due to the more recent
661 and less conservative wind load model adopted in this study for the US framework [25] compared to
662 the load models assumed in [8,11]. Finally, and as for the vertical deflection limit states, it can be noted
663 that the annual reliability indices β_{1yr} reported in Table 9 are roughly comparable to those calculated
664 in [20] for the ultimate limit state and a reference period of 50 years.

665 **6. CONCLUSIONS**

666 Most relevant international standards for steel structures [2,3,5,6] have recently taken major steps
667 towards changing the paradigm of structural design by incorporating provisions of *analysis-by-design*
668 approaches. These provisions will allow not only the design of more integrated, lighter and more
669 efficient structures, but will also contribute to the simplification and acceleration of the design process.
670 However, since at present no specific system reliability requirements or acceptable target reliability
671 indices are provided in these standards for system-based design approaches, recent research efforts have
672 focussed on the calibration of suitable system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_s in the
673 form of the Direct Design Method (DDM) for hot-rolled [7-10] and cold-formed [11,12] steel frames,
674 racks [13], scaffolding structures [14] and stainless steel portal frames [19,20]. Nevertheless, since

675 advanced design approaches potentially result in lighter structures, serviceability issues may become
676 more important than for the traditional *two-step* design approach, especially when materials
677 characterized by a nonlinear stress-strain behaviour are considered. Thus, this paper sets out an explicit
678 analysis framework for assessing serviceability reliability at system level and presents the serviceability
679 limit state reliability assessment of stainless steel frames designed using the DDM.

680 Two different serviceability limit states were assessed in this study, *viz.* excessive deflections under
681 gravity loads and excessive lateral drifts under wind loads. The serviceability reliability analyses were
682 based on six stainless steel portal frames subjected to different load cases, and included the three most
683 common stainless steel grades (i.e., austenitic EN 1.4301/ASTM 304, duplex EN 1.4462/ASTM 2205
684 and ferritic EN 1.4003/ASTM UNS S40977 grades). The variability of the vertical and lateral system
685 stiffnesses was determined from extensive finite element simulations that accounted for the randomness
686 of relevant variables (geometric properties, initial imperfections, material properties, connection
687 behaviour and model uncertainty). In conjunction with the serviceability load combinations specified
688 in prEN 1990 [36], ASCE 7 [39] and AS/NZS 1170.0 [40], and the stochastic models characterizing the
689 variability of the loads, reliability indices corresponding to vertical deflections and lateral drifts were
690 calculated and compared with the relevant target reliability indices for different design frameworks.
691 Average annual reliability indices β_{1yr} obtained for the vertical deflection serviceability were 3.19, 2.56
692 and 2.53 for the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks, respectively, while the β_{1yr} values calibrated
693 for the lateral drift serviceability were 2.70, 2.01 and 2.12, respectively. The results indicated that the
694 reliabilities for roof drift were generally lower than those calculated for vertical deflections, and that
695 when the system safety $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system resistance ϕ_S factors recommended in [19,20] for stainless steel
696 frames are adopted, the reliability indices calibrated for vertical deflections and lateral drifts lie above
697 or very close to the target values prescribed in the different frameworks.

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TABLES

Table 1. Summary of system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ and resistance factors ϕ_s for the direct ultimate limit state design of cold-formed stainless steel frames [19,20].

Loading type	Eurocode framework	US framework	Australian framework
Gravity loads	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15$	$\phi_s = 0.95$	$\phi_s = 0.90$
Wind loads	$\gamma_{M,s} = 1.20$	$\phi_s = 0.90$	$\phi_s = 0.90$

Table 2. Key parameters defining baseline stainless steel portal frames (adapted from [19,20]).

Portal frame	Stainless steel family and grade	Cross-section	Span [m]	Height at eaves [m]	Height at roof ridge [m]
Frame 1	Austenitic (1.4301-304)	150×100×4	8.0	4.8	6.0
Frame 2		250×150×4	10.0	6.4	7.0
Frame 3	Duplex (1.4462-2205)	150×100×4	8.0	4.8	6.0
Frame 4		250×150×4	12.0	6.6	7.4
Frame 5	Ferritic (1.4003-S40977)	150×100×4	8.0	4.8	6.0
Frame 6		250×150×4	11.0	6.5	7.2

Table 3. Nominal initial stiffness values adopted at the base, apex and eave connections (from [19,20]).

Portal frame	Nominal initial stiffness [kNm/rad]		
	Base joints	Apex joint	Eave joints
Frame 1	4000	6600	6400
Frame 2	5000*	7500	7000
Frame 3	4000	6600	6400
Frame 4	5000*	9500	9000
Frame 5	4000	6600	6400
Frame 6	5000*	8500	8000

* Pinned base connections were assumed for the gravity load cases in these frames.

Table 4. Statistics of loads.

Framework	Load type	Reference period	Mean	COV	Statistical distribution	Reference
Eurocode framework	Dead load G	-	$1.00 \cdot G_k$	0.10	Normal	[50]
	Imposed load Q	50 years	$0.80 \cdot Q_k$	0.25	Extreme Type I	[19]
	Imposed load Q	8 years	$0.52 \cdot Q_k$	0.32	Extreme Type I	-
	Wind load W	50 years	$0.72 \cdot W_k^*$	0.36	Extreme Type I	[20]
	Wind load W	10 years	$0.49 \cdot W_k^*$	0.50	Extreme Type I	-
US framework	Dead load D	-	$1.05 \cdot D_n$	0.10	Normal	[51]
	Imposed load L	50 years	$1.00 \cdot L_n$	0.25	Extreme Type I	[51]
	Imposed load L	8 years	$0.65 \cdot L_n$	0.32	Extreme Type I	[52]
	Wind load W	50 years	$0.75 \cdot W_{n,50}^*$	0.35	Extreme Type I	[25]
	Wind load W	10 years	$0.51 \cdot W_{n,50}^*$	0.50	Extreme Type I	-
	Wind load W	10 years	$0.33 \cdot W_{n,700}^\dagger$	0.50	Extreme Type I	-
Australian framework	Dead load G	-	$1.05 \cdot G_n$	0.10	Normal	[12]
	Imposed load Q	50 years	$1.00 \cdot Q_n$	0.25	Extreme Type I	[19]
	Imposed load Q	8 years	$0.65 \cdot Q_n$	0.32	Extreme Type I	-
	Wind load W	50 years	$0.68 \cdot W_{n,50}^*$	0.39	Extreme Type I	[53]
	Wind load W	10 years	$0.47 \cdot W_{n,50}^*$	0.50	Extreme Type I	-
	Wind load W	10 years	$0.32 \cdot W_{n,500}^\ddagger$	0.50	Extreme Type I	-

* Nominal wind load is based on a return period of T=50 years.

† Nominal wind load is based on a return period of T=700 years.

‡ Nominal wind load is based on a return period of T=500 years.

Table 5. Allowable vertical deflection and lateral drift limits for steel structures.

SLS criteria	Limit	Structure type	Loads	Reference
Vertical deflection at apex, $\delta_{a,v}$	s/125	Not accessible resilient roof	Imposed load	[36]
	s/250	Accessible resilient roof		
	s/240	Roof members	Imposed load	[39]
	s/300	Roof members	Long-term gravity loads	[40]
	s/200	Roofs in general	Total loads	[56]
	s/250	Roofs in general	Imposed load	[56]
	s/360	Frames with pitch angle $> 3^\circ$	Dead load	[58]
	s/500	Frames with pitch angle $< 3^\circ$		
	s/240	-	Imposed load	[58]
	s/150	-	Wind load	[58]
s/250	-	-	[59]	
Lateral drifts at eaves, $\delta_{a,w}$	$H_1/300$	-	Wind load	[8,11]
	$H_1/400$	Single storey buildings	-	[36]
	$H_1/600-H_1/400$	-	Wind load	[39]
	$H_1/500$	Side sway in columns	Wind load	[40]
	$H_1/400$	-	Wind load	[49]
	$H_1/150$	Portal frames without gantry crane	Total loads	[56]
	$H_1/150$	Portal frames without fragile elements	Total loads	[57]
	$H_1/300$	Single-storey buildings with horizontal roofs without fragile elements	Total loads	[57]
	$H_1/150$	Portal frame with metal cladding	Service wind	[58]
	$H_1/240$	Portal frame with masonry cladding	Service wind	[58]
	$H_1/150$	Portal frame	-	[59]
	$H_1/100$	Profiled metal sheeting	Wind,	[60]
$H_1/200$	Precast concrete units	imposed loads		

Note: s is the frame span and H_1 is the height at eaves.

Table 6. Statistics of initial frame stiffness for stainless steel frames under gravity loads and combined gravity and wind loads.

Frame	Gravity loads		Dead and wind loads GW1		Dead and wind loads GW2		Dead and wind loads GW3	
	$\bar{K}_{v,0}$ [N/mm]	$V_{Kv,0}$	$\bar{K}_{w,0}$ [N/mm / mm]	$V_{Kw,0}$	$\bar{K}_{w,0}$ [N/mm / mm]	$V_{Kw,0}$	$\bar{K}_{w,0}$ [N/mm / mm]	$V_{Kw,0}$
Frame 1	474.4	0.066	29.87	0.088	29.63	0.081	29.67	0.082
Frame 2	730.9	0.067	44.91	0.078	45.01	0.076	45.02	0.077
Frame 3	489.6	0.056	31.60	0.077	31.50	0.077	31.43	0.077
Frame 4	499.3	0.070	38.22	0.078	38.33	0.077	38.39	0.077
Frame 5	476.6	0.079	31.18	0.090	31.26	0.089	31.31	0.089
Frame 6	602.5	0.078	41.53	0.082	41.58	0.082	41.64	0.081

Table 7. Comparison between elastic deflections (or drifts) with the corresponding total deflections (or drifts) for design serviceability loads in different load scenarios.

Frame	Gravity loads $d_{v,el}/d_{v,tot}$		Combined gravity and wind loads, GW1 $d_{w,el}/d_{w,tot}$		Combined gravity and wind loads, GW2 $d_{w,el}/d_{w,tot}$		Combined gravity and wind loads, GW3 $d_{w,el}/d_{w,tot}$	
	Mean	COV	Mean	COV	Mean	COV	Mean	COV
Frame 1	0.964	0.017	0.948	0.024	0.948	0.037	0.944	0.033
Frame 2	0.996	0.005	0.972	0.033	0.973	0.030	0.968	0.038
Frame 3	0.952	0.023	0.965	0.016	0.962	0.014	0.960	0.014
Frame 4	0.997	0.004	0.991	0.016	0.990	0.013	0.990	0.012
Frame 5	0.989	0.008	0.965	0.012	0.964	0.017	0.962	0.017
Frame 6	0.986	0.015	0.985	0.021	0.984	0.022	0.982	0.024
Average	0.981	0.022	0.971	0.026	0.971	0.027	0.968	0.029

Table 8. Statistics of vertical stiffness and reliability indices for stainless steel frames under gravity loads (for an imposed-to-dead load ratio $\alpha = 2.0$).

Design framework	Frame	\bar{K}_v [N/mm]	$V_{K,v}$	$K_{v,n}$ [N/mm]	β_{8yrs}	β_{1yr}
Eurocode framework	Frame 1	457.5	0.083	502.1	2.62	3.27
	Frame 2	727.6	0.073	781.6	2.52	3.18
	Frame 3	466.2	0.079	508.4	2.59	3.24
	Frame 4	498.0	0.073	526.8	2.46	3.13
	Frame 5	471.5	0.087	502.1	2.49	3.15
	Frame 6	594.1	0.093	640.6	2.54	3.20
	Average	-	-	-	2.54	3.19
US framework	Frame 1	457.5	0.083	487.4	1.75	2.57
	Frame 2	727.6	0.073	746.1	1.57	2.43
	Frame 3	466.2	0.079	508.4	1.85	2.65
	Frame 4	498.0	0.073	525.4	1.70	2.53
	Frame 5	471.5	0.087	501.9	1.75	2.57
	Frame 6	594.1	0.093	640.9	1.81	2.61
	Average	-	-	-	1.74	2.56
Australian framework	Frame 1	457.5	0.083	491.7	1.78	2.59
	Frame 2	727.6	0.073	759.6	1.62	2.47
	Frame 3	466.2	0.079	508.4	1.85	2.64
	Frame 4	498.0	0.073	525.4	1.68	2.51
	Frame 5	471.5	0.087	491.7	1.62	2.47
	Frame 6	594.1	0.093	627.5	1.69	2.52
	Average	-	-	-	1.70	2.53

Table 9. Statistics of lateral stiffness and reliability indices for stainless steel frames under combined gravity and wind loads (for dead load level GW1).

Design framework	Frame	\bar{K}_w [N/mm / mm]	$V_{K,w}$	$K_{w,n}$ [N/mm / mm]	β_{10yrs}	β_{1yr}
Eurocode framework	Frame 1	28.33	0.112	29.28	1.83	2.71
	Frame 2	43.67	0.111	47.33	1.92	2.77
	Frame 3	30.49	0.094	30.26	1.78	2.67
	Frame 4	37.86	0.093	38.86	1.81	2.69
	Frame 5	30.08	0.102	30.50	1.78	2.67
	Frame 6	40.89	0.103	42.63	1.84	2.71
	Average	-	-	-	1.83	2.70
US framework	Frame 1	28.33	0.112	28.10	0.76	1.96
	Frame 2	43.67	0.111	46.49	0.91	2.06
	Frame 3	30.49	0.094	30.59	0.78	1.97
	Frame 4	37.86	0.093	39.10	0.85	2.02
	Frame 5	30.08	0.102	30.62	0.81	1.99
	Frame 6	40.89	0.103	43.05	0.89	2.04
	Average	-	-	-	0.83	2.01
Australian framework	Frame 1	28.33	0.112	28.76	0.98	2.11
	Frame 2	43.67	0.111	46.80	1.10	2.19
	Frame 3	30.49	0.094	30.59	0.96	2.09
	Frame 4	37.86	0.093	39.10	1.03	2.13
	Frame 5	30.08	0.102	29.29	0.90	2.05
	Frame 6	40.89	0.103	42.26	1.02	2.13
	Average	-	-	-	1.00	2.12

FIGURES

Figure 1. Typical joint configurations considered for the baseline stainless steel portal frames.

Figure 2. Gravity and combined dead plus wind load patterns adopted in the analysis (from [19,20]).

Figure 3. Elastic and plastic components of deflections (or drifts) in stainless steel frames.

Figure 4. Typical histograms for initial vertical frame stiffness $K_{V,0}$ of stainless steel frames under gravity loads for Frames 1 to 6.

Figure 5. Typical histograms for initial lateral frame stiffness $K_{w,0}$ of stainless steel frames under the GW1 dead and wind load case for Frames 1 to 6.

Figure 6. Typical histograms for initial lateral frame stiffness $K_{w,0}$ of stainless steel frames under the GW3 dead and wind load case for Frames 1 to 6.